

AWARENESS OF LIFE SKILLS IN TRAINEE TEACHERS

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Abstract-

This study was conducted to assess the life skill awareness of trainee teachers in training course. Modern society is the quick, almost breath-taking rate at which social change takes place. In a traditional society change is slow that the conservatism of the educational system does comparatively little harm. The conclusion suggests that the present teacher training course does not included the life skill education of trainee teachers.

Key word- Life skill, trainee-teacher, training, awareness.

Introduction-

In modern education system to be a living force, must derive its strength from the strength of the spirit, modernization aims amongst other things at creating an economy of plenty which would offer to every individual a larger way of life and a wider variety of choices. Education the most important and dominating face of human life have very well been addressed by framers of our constitution under fundamental rights and directive principles of state policy. Learning at this stage may be characterized by group activities, leadership, games and activities directed to promote socialization and life skills awareness among trainee teacher and help them in the process of attaining physical, mental and emotional development. Approaches in developing life skills and the formation of good habits and togetherness need to be undertaken. Education has to be relevant to the needs and aspirations of the people living in the present fast changing society. Even more important is the role of education in achieving social and national integration. Indian society is hierarchical, stratified and deficient in vertical mobility. The curriculum of teacher education should be considerably improved. But in programming life skills education is needed at all levels and in all courses and it will possible for us to examine all aspects. The rapid rates of consumption led to faster depletion of resources. Life skills-based education is now recognized as a methodology to address a variety of issues of child and youth development and thematic responses including as expressed in UNGASS on HIV/AIDS (2001), UNGASS on Children (2002), World Youth Report (2003), World Program for Human Rights

Education (2004), UN Decade on Education for Sustainable Development (2005), UN Secretary General's Study on Violence Against Children (2006), 51st Commission on the Status of Women (2007), and the World Development Report (2007).

Life skills have been defined as *"the abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life"* (WHO).

'Adaptive' means that a person is flexible in approach and is able to adjust in different circumstances.

'Positive behaviour' implies that a person is forward looking and even in difficult situations, can find a ray of hope and opportunities to find solutions.

Need of the study-

The progress of modernization will therefore be directly related to the pace of education advance and the one sure way to modernize quickly is to spread education, to produce educated and skilled teachers and train an adequate and competent intelligentsia. The Indian society of today is heir to a great culture. Life skills have been recognized all over the world as a variable tool for creating life skills awareness among trainee-teachers.

Objective of the Study-

The main objective of the study was to assess the life skills awareness of trainee-teachers in the training. To increase the level of training of trainee-teachers to develop self-confidence, promote the spirit of inquiry.

Methodology-

The investigate was conducted through normative survey method. The trainee-teachers of B. Ed. training programme were treated as sample of the study. The questionnaire tool for assessing the life skills awareness of trainee-teachers. The test was administrated in the training programme. Collected questionnaire were scored carefully according to the questions out of a total 80 trainee-teachers were studied in the training.

Analysis and interpretation of data -

Life skills Awareness of Trainee-teachers in the Training.

Sr No.	Question related to life skills	Total No	Mean	Median	S.D.	Above Median		Below Median		T Value	Levels of significance
						No.	%	No.	%		
1	Total Sample	80	49.36	49	4.94	48	61.25	32	38.75		
2	Self-awareness	45	49.22	50	4.99	26	57.78	19	42.22		

3	Empathy	35	49.4 9	49	4.82	20	57.14	15	42.8 6	0.39	N.S.
4	Critical thinking	49	49.7 7	50	4.73	36	73.47	13	26.5 3		
5	Creative thinking	31	49.2 7	49	4.99	20	64.51	11	35.4 9		
6	Decision making	21	49.3 2	50	4.69	14	66.66	7	33.3 3		
7	Problem Solving	59	49.4 2	49	5.28	35	59.32	24	60.6 8		
8	Effective communication	59	49.2 2	49	5.28	35	59.32	24	60.6 8		
9	Interpersonal relationship	49	49.7 7	50	4.73	36	73.47	13	26.5 3		
10	Stress	59	49.2 2	49	5.28	35	59.32	24	60.6 8		
11	Emotion	45	49.2 2	50	4.99	26	57.78	19	42.2 2		

Graph No. 1

The above questionnaire the median value are considered as favorable awareness and below the median values are considered as indicating unfavorable awareness towards life skills of trainee-teachers in training. The life skills is depend upon the trainee teachers attitudes in the training course .The above table shows that the percentage of problem solving in trainee-teachers it is valuable for trainee-teachers. The mean difference was found out and was used for testing any significant difference in the perception among the various sub-sample groups. Among 80 trainee-teachers taken for the study, 61.25% were good awareness towards life skills and 38.75% were not enough awareness of life skills. The self-awareness, Empathy, Creative thinking, Decision making, Critical thinking are relatively satisfactory.

Conclusion

The self-awareness of trainee-teachers develops from their perceptions of themselves in social and physical environments and from the reactions of others to their behavior. The critical thinking of trainee-teachers can contribute to health by helping us to recognize and assess the factors that influence attitudes and behavior, such as values, peer pressure, practical and other teaching lesson. Trainee –teachers have decision making helps us to deal constructively with decisions about our lives. Life skills provides opportunities for trainee-teachers to learn from one another and practice turning to another in problem solving.

Provides an excellent strategy for practicing skills; experiencing how one might handle a potential situation in real life.

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